

Primordial Charge and Mass at the Planck Scale via Reissner-Nordström Spacetime and Relativistic Quantum Theory

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Abstract

The usual paradigm for quantum gravity at the Planck Scale of considering only G , \hbar and c as fundamental physical constants is enlarged with electric charge. The resulting Planck Particle acts as an Extremal Black Hole source of a Reissner-Nordström spacetime. For radial geodesics located between $r = Q^2/(2Mc^2)$ and $r = Q^2/Mc^2$, M and Q being the mass and charge origin of the spacetime geometry, the gravitational force is repulsive, independently of the gravitational constant G and the sign of the charge. Quantum calculations via Dirac equation predict bound fundamental states between Planck charged particles and electrons and protons with binding energies $-1900eV$ and $-3.43MeV$ respectively and expectation and maximum probability distances for the electron, or positron, of $6.76422 \times 10^{-10}cm.$ and $4.50397 \times 10^{-10}cm.$ respectively. The results of this study suggest a possible equality between the strength of gravitational and electromagnetic interactions at the beginning of the Planck Era.

1 Introduction

Finding a connection between quantum mechanics and general relativity is usually done by the heuristic argument of considering the Compton wavelength \hbar/Mc of a certain particle of mass M and its gravitational radius

GM/c^2 , both magnitudes being essential ingredients of what is known as the Planck Scale which in its more economical way is solely determined by the 3 fundamental constants \hbar , c and G .

In principle, there is not any a priori strong reason to assume that at the Planck scale the source of the primordial spacetime is devoid of charge. The question is what should be considered as essential ingredients in the Planck era. It is obvious that if we consider some particle with mass there is an associated gravitational field and if we add charge then we also have a gravitational field albeit of a different kind which in this case, assuming that general relativity is applicable at the Planck Scale, should be a Reissner-Nordström Spacetime. We shall thus assume that mass and charge are fundamental aspects of physical reality and explore its consequences.

The first relation connecting classical dynamics with quantum theory is the well known equality, via the principle of uncertainty, between the Compton Wavelength and the gravitational radius

$$\frac{\hbar}{Mc} = \frac{GM}{c^2}. \quad (1)$$

Considering charge on equal footing as mass, if in some primordial state we have a particle with a charge Q , on dimensional grounds, we may define a length

$$\frac{\hbar}{Mc} = \frac{Q^2}{Mc^2}. \quad (2)$$

The first definition leads to $M = \sqrt{\hbar c/G}$ the second to $Q = \sqrt{\hbar c}$ and equating the right hand side of both:

$$GM^2 - Q^2 = 0. \quad (3)$$

This last condition defines what is called an *Extremal Black Hole*.

Although this value of electric charge, given by the square root of the product of two fundamental constants, is already known, it is rarely considered and as it is obtained from dimensional analysis alone it lacks a sound theoretical justification. Further analysis in next section from the general relativity perspective will confirm the precedent values and reveal some new features that might be significative for a new insight in Quantum Gravity.

In a recent paper [1] it was noticed the fact that from the standpoint of General Relativity (In the case here studied, the Spacetime induced

by the Reissner-Nordström Metric), all charged elementary particles and some composite ones are Naked Singularities (NS), defined by the condition $GM^2 - Q^2 < 0$ (in contradiction with the Cosmic Censorship Principle). Even quarks which masses are yet poorly known (2-4 Mev for the Up and Down quarks) might also be NS. The *Ansatz* here adopted is that the hierarchy of possible elementary particles has an end at the Planck Mass, being such a particle no longer a NS but an Extremal Black Hole.

A common feature of RN black holes and NS is the existence, as previously reported in [3] [4] and more recently in [1], of a distance of null gravitational force located at a radial distance $Q^2/(Mc^2)$ from the singularity, being the force repulsive below this distance.

In order of explaining how the above mentioned distance of null gravitational force and other features of relevance arise, the next section will be devoted to the study of radial geodesics in the RN metric.

2 Radial Geodesics in Reissner-Nordström Space-time and extrapolation to the Planck Scale

In spherical coordinates $x^\alpha = (ct, r, \theta, \phi)$ and metric signature (+ - - -), the element of arch parametrized by proper time τ is

$$d\tau^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{GQ^2}{c^4 r^2}\right) c^2 dt^2 - \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{GQ^2}{c^4 r^2}\right)^{-1} dr^2 - r^2 d\theta^2 - r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2. \quad (4)$$

For the study of radial geodesics, a convenient start point is the Lagrangian [2]

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{GQ^2}{c^4 r^2}\right) c^2 \dot{t}^2 - \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{GQ^2}{c^4 r^2}\right)^{-1} \dot{r}^2 \right]. \quad (5)$$

(dot meaning derivative respect to proper time τ). Together with the Euler-Lagrange equations

$$\frac{d}{d\tau} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{x}^\alpha} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial x^\alpha} = 0. \quad (6)$$

For $x^0 = ct$, if we restrict to radial geodesics and since the coordinate time does not explicitly appears in the lagrangian, the corresponding canonical momentum is a constant of the motion \bar{E} that can be interpreted as the

energy per unit mass:

$$u_0 = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{t}} = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{GQ^2}{c^4 r^2} \right) u^0 = \tilde{E}. \quad (7)$$

If we drop a test particle from infinity on a radial trajectory beginning at rest, the constant \tilde{E} is simply unit. Then, from the last equation and (5):

$$u^0 = c \frac{dt}{d\tau} = \frac{c}{\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{GQ^2}{c^4 r^2} \right)} \quad (8)$$

and

$$u^1 = \frac{dr}{d\tau} = \sqrt{\frac{2GM}{r} - \frac{GQ^2}{c^2 r^2}}. \quad (9)$$

The Christoffel symbols for the radial coordinate are:

$$\Gamma_{rr}^r = -\frac{\frac{GM}{c^2} - \frac{GQ^2}{c^2}}{r\left(r^2 - \frac{2GM}{c^2}r + \frac{GQ^2}{c^2}\right)}, \quad \Gamma_{tt}^r = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{GQ^2}{c^2 r^2} \right) \left(\frac{GM}{c^2 r^2} - \frac{GQ^2}{c^2 r^3} \right). \quad (10)$$

$$\Gamma_{tr}^r = \frac{\frac{GM}{c^2} - \frac{GQ^2}{c^2}}{r\left(r^2 - \frac{2GM}{c^2}r + \frac{GQ^2}{c^2 r^2}\right)}$$

From the precedent relations and the geodesic equation, the radial acceleration relative to the proper time is

$$\frac{d^2 r}{d\tau^2} = \frac{GM}{r^2} - \frac{GQ^2}{c^2 r^3}. \quad (11)$$

Irrespective of the value of the gravitational constant G and the sign of the charge, the right hand side is null for

$$r_{NF} = \frac{Q^2}{Mc^2} \quad (12)$$

and negative (repulsive) below.

The well known expression determining the Event and Cauchy Horizons in RN spacetime is

$$r = \frac{1}{c^2} \left(GM \pm \sqrt{G(GM^2 - Q^2)} \right). \quad (13)$$

For $GM^2 - Q^2 > 0$ both kind of Horizons exist. The case $GM^2 - Q^2 = 0$ corresponds to a so called Extremal Black Hole, while for $GM^2 - Q^2 <$

0 we have a NS (as already mentioned, to my notice, all known charged elementary particles belong to this class).

From the first of the preceding two equations and (2) we see that the radial distance of null force equals its Compton Wavelength. Furthermore, the last equation is only compatible with (1) if the condition of an extremal black hole $GM^2 - Q^2 = 0$ holds. Consequently, for an extremal black hole its mass determines its electric charge (the opposite statement being also true), G acting as a conversion factor dependent on the system of units.

The condition $GM^2 - Q^2 = 0$ can be interpreted as an effective equality of the strength of the electric and the gravitational interaction at the Planck Scale. We further notice that if at the beginning there was a charged Planck particle and since in this case G is determined by

$$G = \frac{Q^2}{M^2},$$

it is the value of this ratio that might determine the bulk properties of matter in our Universe at the present cosmic time.

From (11) it is immediate to obtain that the maximum repulsive acceleration corresponds to a distance ¹

$$r = \frac{Q^2}{2Mc^2},$$

equal to $8.08117 \times 10^{-34} \text{cm}$ located below the event horizon, the acceleration being given by

$$\frac{d^2r}{d\tau^2} = -\frac{4GM^3c^4}{Q^4}, \quad (14)$$

having the numerical value $-2.2243 \times 10^{54} \text{cm.s}^{-2}$ in the case of the Planck Mass. On the other hand, for such a distance and from (9), the radial velocity is null. For the distance corresponding to null gravitational force $r_{NF} = Q^2/Mc^2$, the radial component of the velocity given by (9) is

$$u_r = c\sqrt{\frac{GM^2}{Q^2}}, \quad (15)$$

maximal and equal to c , as measured by a local observer, for any extremal black hole.

¹A distance equal to one-half the Compton Wavelength already appears in relativistic quantum mechanics in the Zitterbewegung phenomenon related to the oscillation inner frequency of a free particle equal to $2mc^2/\hbar$. See [6], [5]

From the precedent results, we can define a dimensionless coupling constant α_p as

$$\alpha_p = \frac{GM^2}{\hbar c} = \frac{Q^2}{\hbar c} = 1. \quad (16)$$

Recalling how the classical radius of the electron was defined:

$$E = mc^2 = \frac{e^2}{r}. \quad (17)$$

Since for the Planck charge (about 11.7 times the electron charge) $Q = \sqrt{\hbar c}$:

$$E = \frac{Q^2}{r} = \frac{Q^2}{\hbar/Mc} = Mc^2, \quad (18)$$

suggesting an electric origin of the Planck mass.

3 Classical versus quantum mechanical results at the Planck Scale

In what follows natural units ($\hbar = c = 1$) will be adopted.

From the condition

$$GM^2 - Q^2 = 0, \quad (19)$$

then

$$Q = \sqrt{GM}. \quad (20)$$

Generally valid for any RN extreme black hole. For M equal to the Planck Mass $M_p = 1/\sqrt{G}$, and we find

$$Q = 1(eV)^0 \quad (21)$$

(about 11.7 times the electron or positron charge). (Note that r_{NF} is also located at the only horizon at $L_p = 1/M_p$).

As it is only G which determines the value of M_p , the previous numerical value is independent of any specific value of the gravitational constant thus setting a limit for electric charge. Since charge is a Lorentz invariant quantity $Q = 1$ might perhaps be interpreted as the maximum electric charge that an elementary particle can hold in the same sense that $c = 1$ is the maximum velocity.

Most of what has been obtained until now is strictly valid only for a test neutral particle of negligible mass. If the test particle is charged, invoking the principle of general covariance, the non-geodesic equation of motion is

$$\frac{d^2 x^\alpha}{d\tau^2} + \Gamma_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha u^\beta u^\gamma = \frac{e}{m} F_\beta^\alpha u^\beta, \quad (22)$$

being F_β^α the electromagnetic field tensor in spherical coordinates.

For radial trajectories, in natural units, the equation of motion replacing (11) is

$$\frac{d^2 r}{d\tau^2} = \left(\frac{GM}{r^2} - \frac{GQ^2}{r^3} \right) - \frac{e}{m} \frac{Q}{r^2}. \quad (23)$$

From the condition $GM^2 - Q^2 = 0$ valid for any extremal black hole $G = Q^2/M^2$ and the former equation can be written only in terms of Q as

$$\frac{d^2 r}{d\tau^2} = \left(\frac{Q^2}{Mr^2} - \frac{Q^4}{M^2 r^3} \right) - \frac{e}{m} \frac{Q}{r^2}. \quad (24)$$

To find the radial distance of null acceleration for the test charged particle the equation to solve is

$$\left(\frac{Q^2}{Mr^2} - \frac{Q^4}{M^2 r^3} \right) - \frac{e}{m} \frac{Q}{r^2} = 0. \quad (25)$$

With the result:

$$r_{NF} = \frac{Q^2}{\left(1 - \frac{eM}{mQ}\right) M}. \quad (26)$$

Considering as admissible both signs of charge for the Planck particle: $Q = \pm 1$ and also the possibility of electrons and positrons, from the former relation, invariant under the change of sign of both particles, we see that classical general relativity would not distinguish between positive Planck particles and electrons and the opposite scenario.

In the case of the electron and Q positive, the factor eM/mQ is -2.03561×10^{21} leading to $r_{NF} = 4.02372 \times 10^{-50} eV^{-1}$ corresponding to a rather small distance of $7.93961 \times 10^{-55} cm$. It will be seen below how a relativistic quantum approach will give quite different results.

Turning now to the quantum picture and regarding the positive or negative Planck particle as a fermionic spin 1/2 particle, it seems possible to

apply the Dirac equation and its solution in the similar Hydrogen Atom case to the Planck particle relativistic quantum dynamics. In natural units, the normalized spin-up wave function solution of the Dirac equation for the Hydrogen atom in its ground state is [7] [8] :

$$\psi(r, \theta, \varphi) = \frac{(2m\alpha)^{3/2}}{\sqrt{4\pi}} \sqrt{\frac{1+\gamma}{2\Gamma(1+2\gamma)}} (2m\alpha r)^{\gamma-1} e^{-m\alpha r} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ \frac{i(1-\gamma)}{\alpha} \cos \theta \\ \frac{i(1-\gamma)}{\alpha} \sin \theta i\varphi \end{pmatrix}, \quad (27)$$

with

$$\gamma = \sqrt{1 - \alpha^2}.$$

Γ being the Gamma function of argument $(1+2\gamma)$, m the mass of the electron and α the fine structure constant. However, there is now an important point that should be considered. The fine structure constant, or coupling constant α , is defined for two identical charges while in the case of an electron and the positive charged Planck particle the charges are different. In conventional

units, the coupling constant $\alpha = e^2/\hbar c$ should be replaced by

$$\alpha_p = \frac{eQ}{\hbar c} = \frac{e\sqrt{\hbar c}}{\hbar c} = \frac{e}{\sqrt{\hbar c}}. \quad (28)$$

From (27), and its complex conjugate, it is straightforward to see that the distribution of probability is isotropic:

$$\psi^* \psi \propto \left[1 + \frac{(1-\gamma)^2}{\alpha_p^2} \cos^2 \theta + \frac{(1-\gamma)^2}{\alpha_p^2} \sin^2 \theta \right]. \quad (29)$$

The next step is to find the distances, from the origin, where the probability of finding the electron is maximal and the expectation value. From the previous expression and (27):

$$\psi^* \psi = \frac{1}{4\pi} 8m^3 \alpha_p^3 \frac{1}{\Gamma(1+2\gamma)} (2m\alpha_p r) e^{-2m\alpha_p r}. \quad (30)$$

The expectation value

$$\langle r \rangle = \int_0^\infty \psi^* r \psi 4\pi r^2 dr, \quad (31)$$

follows by making $2m\alpha_p r = x$ and solving the integral

$$\int_0^{\infty} e^{-x} x^{2\gamma+1} dx = \Gamma(2\gamma + 2), \quad (32)$$

together with the recursion formula

$$\Gamma(2\gamma + 2) = (2\gamma + 1)\Gamma(2\gamma + 1).$$

The calculations can be carried out without much difficulty with the result:

$$\langle \psi | r | \psi \rangle = \frac{1}{m} \left[\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha_p^2} - 1} + \frac{1}{2\alpha_p} \right]. \quad (33)$$

In our case and since in natural units $\alpha_p = e = 0.08542(eV)^0$ and $m = 0.511005MeV$, the result is

$$\langle r \rangle = 3.42804 \times 10^{-5}(eV)^{-1}.$$

equivalent to 6.76422×10^{-10} cm.

In order to find the radial distance of the electron where the probability of finding the electron is maximum, we consider first:

$$\psi^* \psi r^2 = \frac{2m^3 \alpha_p^3 (2m\alpha_p)^{2(\gamma-1)}}{\pi \Gamma(1+2\gamma)} r^{2\gamma} e^{-2m\alpha_p r}. \quad (34)$$

As $\Gamma(1+2\gamma)$ is a magnitude depending only on γ , the radius of maximum probability comes out after solving for r the equation resulting from:

$$\frac{d}{dr} [r^{2\gamma} \cdot e^{-2m\alpha_p r}] = 0. \quad (35)$$

The result is

$$r_{max} = \frac{1}{m} \sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha_p^2} - 1}. \quad (36)$$

For the electron $r_{max} = 4.50397 \times 10^{-10} cm$ (two order of magnitude lower than the Bohr radius). The total energy is given by

$$E_T = m\sqrt{1 - \alpha_p^2} = 5.09137 \times 10^5 eV \quad (37)$$

and the binding energy

$$E_B = m\sqrt{1 - \alpha_p^2} - m = -1900eV.$$

Since the mass of the Proton is about 1836 times greater than the corresponding to the electron, the previous calculations for the Proton gives values 1836 lower than those for the electron for the expectation value and maximal probability distance.

As for the total and binding energy:

$$E_T = M\sqrt{1 - \alpha_p^2} = 934.826MeV$$

and $E_B = -3.43MeV$ (Of the same order of magnitude of nuclear binding energies in light elements. For the Deuteron: -2.22 MeV).

The previous results are unchanged if we consider positrons or antiprotons and negative Planck particles.

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